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OPPORTUNITIES FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE SERVICE SECTOR IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Abstract: *This article presents practical and analytical views on the specifics of economic activity in the service and tourism sectors during the development of the Fourth Industrial Revolution.*

Keywords: *Service economy, tourism, fourth industrial revolution, economic activity, digital transformation, digital economy*

The service economy and tourism are among the most promising economic activities during the development of the fourth industrial revolution. In developed countries, the service economy is becoming increasingly important, the volume of production of services and income from them are growing.

According to the classification of the World Trade Organization, the service economy includes more than 150 different types of services. These include business services, communications services, financial services, educational services, tourism and related services, transportation services, transportation and recreation, and cultural and sporting events. From this we can say that the service sector is currently the main type of economic activity. Almost everyone uses one service or another.

The current stage of economic development is associated with the Fourth Industrial Revolution, characterized by the digitalization of all economic activity. K. Schwab, President of the World Economic Forum in Davos, argues that the fourth industrial revolution (Industry 4.0) is unparalleled in terms of scale and complexity. It is based on fundamentally new technologies that have emerged in recent years, including artificial intelligence, robotics, big data processing technologies, blockchain, and more.¹

¹ Сервис plus Том 12 2018 №1 / Service plus Volume 12 2018 #1

"INNOVATIVE ACHIEVEMENTS IN SCIENCE 2022"

Digital transformation is a series of socio-economic changes in society, including globalization processes, changes in local and global market regulation, increased pressure on prices and market volatility, increased population mobility, environmental protection and social responsibility, increased humanity and attention. harmonizes with. In addition, digital transformation also affects such indicators as the quality of life, well-being and happiness of the population.

Digital transformation and socio-economic changes have led to the formation of a digital type of production and a digital type of consumption of goods. These processes developed rapidly during the Fourth Industrial Revolution. Each industrial revolution occupies a special place in the development of mankind.

1 table. Brief description of industrial revolution technologies²

1800s Industry 1.0	1900s Industry 2.0	1970s Industry 3.0	2015+ Industry 4.0	2030+ Industry 5.0
The invention of steam engines	Mass production. Invention of electric motors and internal combustion engines.	Electronics. Industrial robots, information technology and production automation. The advent of the Internet	Digital forms of delivery. Data analysis. Digital products, smart manufacturing	Processes of virtualization. Virtual communication with clients

It is not difficult to feel the impact of the digital economy on all aspects of human life. Today, every second inhabitant of the planet has access to the Internet and can use the services of the digital services economy, social networks, and various instant messengers have already become an integral attribute of interpersonal communication.

In most countries of the world, the service sector has been determining the key macroeconomic indicators of the country over the past three decades. The introduction of new technologies in industry and agriculture, as well as the

² David B., Chalou R., Yin C. Collaborative Systems & Shared Economy (Uberization): Principles & Case Study. 2016 International Conference on Collaboration Technologies and Systems (CTS), Orlando, FL, 2016,

"INNOVATIVE ACHIEVEMENTS IN SCIENCE 2022"

automation of production, are becoming the main source of employment in the service sector. The development of the service sector is a universal process, determined by a combination of the following trends of the last decade.³

1. Digital transformation of social life and economy;
2. Socio-economic processes of sustainable development, globalization and humanization;
3. Service trends and emergence of hybrid products;
4. Development of a cooperative economy and a joint consumer economy;

The digital economy is a new system of political, economic, scientific, social, cultural and educational relations using digital technologies, and the sustainable development of the service sector is of particular importance in the digital economy.

At the end of 2021, Apple, Microsoft, Saudi Aramco, Alphabet, Amazon, Tesla, Facebook, Berkshire Hathaway INC, Tencent, Visa will top the list of the 10 largest companies in the world with a high level of capitalization. Most of the leading companies in this rating are companies that specialize in providing different levels of services. The digital economy has made the service sector the most profitable, along with large industrial enterprises.

The digital economy involves the digitalization of all business processes related to the creation, promotion and sale of goods and services. Digital data has become a key factor in production, a key asset of companies and plays a key role in all economic activity.

Of particular importance is the information environment of the service business, which provides prompt access to information about the functioning of economic systems in a single global network. The digital infrastructure includes a set of technologies that meet the computing, telecommunications, networking needs of companies operating on a digital basis.

The latest digital technologies included in the digital infrastructure of the new economy include⁴:

- Big data technologies (Big Data)
- Blockchain technologies
- Internet of Things
- neural networks (artificial intelligence)
- virtual and augmented reality technologies
- 3D printing

³ <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000261445>

⁴ https://www.cepal.org/sites/default/files/publication/files/46817/S2000960_en.pdf

"INNOVATIVE ACHIEVEMENTS IN SCIENCE 2022"

- mobile devices
- smart sensors, etc.

Communication services in the service sector, banking services, tourism services are fully focused on the active introduction of digital technologies, many business processes in the service sector have already been rebuilt in accordance with the new paradigm of the digital economy.

The Internet of Things allows you to remotely control many devices (objects) in real time through special sensors. This technology makes the smart home concept widely used in the hospitality industry.

One of the most actively implemented areas of digital technologies is tourism services. It is necessary to create good information support, containing all the information necessary for the traveler to form the attractiveness of the tourist route and ensure the flow of tourists.

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